

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

I am pleased to welcome you all to our first issue of 2018. Allow me to gratefully thank all institutions, reviewers and authors for their valuable support and work. As always, we are interested in submissions of high quality manuscripts and proposals of special issues covering emerging topics and new trends. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues submitting high-quality articles and special issues to our journal. I also want to further broaden our editorial board: if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce three accepted papers from two different countries.

Akim Bassa, Mark Kroll and Roman Kern from Austria introduce their research on GerIE, an OIE system for the German language, which is based on the output of a German dependency parser and a number of handcrafted rules. Flavio L. de Mello and Jose A. M. Xexeo from Brazil analyzes the use of machine learning techniques for the identification of encryption algorithms in ECB and CBC modes. Last but not least, Erick Nilsen Pereira de Souza, Daniela Barreiro Claro and Rafael Glauber from Brazil propose a method for classifying extracted facts based on the similarity of grammatical structures to improve open information systems.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

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